

Web Outlier Mining: Techniques for Mining Web Outliers

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Abstract — Data objects which differ significantly from the remaining data objects are referred to as outliers. Outlier mining in large datasets is an important task in traditional data mining with numerous applications in credit card fraud detection, weather prediction, intrusion detection, and cellular phone cloning fraud detection. Mining Outliers from Web datasets is challenging because of dynamic, unstructured datasets. Web outliers are web data that show significantly different characteristics than other web data taken from the same category. This paper illustrates general framework for web outlier mining. Different techniques and algorithms for mining outliers are discussed.

Keywords— Outlier mining, Web content outliers, Web usage outliers, Web structure outliers, Hyper Graph, SOM.

I. INTRODUCTION

The process of finding useful information from data is called data mining. Fayyad *et al.* [3] describe data mining as the non-trivial process of identifying valid, potentially useful, and understandable patterns in data. Han *et al.* [4] describes data mining as the process of discovering interesting knowledge from large amounts of data stored either in databases, data warehouses, or other information repositories. Data mining involves the entire process of extracting useful information and subsequent analysis of the extracted information for decision making purposes.

Web mining is the application of data mining technique to automatically discover useful and previously unknown information from web documents and services [5,6]. Web mining is becoming more popular as a result of the tremendous growth of the web.

Outliers are observations that deviate so much from other observations that they arouse suspicions that they might have been generated using a different mechanism [5,7]. Outliers identified in web data are referred to as *web outliers* to distinguish them from traditional outliers. The mining process for web outliers is called *web outlier mining*. For example, if it can be established using existing mining techniques that 65% of traders who visit *ebay.com* purchase a product it is unclear what happens to the remaining 35%. This, and many

other queries, can be answered using web outlier mining techniques.

II. CATEGORIES OF WEB MINING

Target data sets for data mining in the context of the web are classified into the following types:

- Content data: The data meant to be conveyed to the web user. Naturally, *web-content mining* is the process of extracting knowledge from the content of web documents (Cohen *et al.* 2000).
- Structure data: The meta data that define the organization of the web information systems. *Web structure mining* is the process of inferring knowledge from the structure of data (Kuo and Wong 2000, Henzinger 2000).
- Usage data: The data collected from user interactions with the web. Web Usage Mining is the process of discovering and interpreting patterns of user access to the web information system (Baumgarten *et al.* 2000).

Web content mining deals with classifying web pages into categories based on their contents so that similar pages can be grouped together to enhance performance. The web-content consists of data of varying types such as text, image, audio, video, hyperlinks, and metadata. The varying content of the web makes web content mining very challenging and multidisciplinary so it encompasses several fields in computer science (i.e., multimedia, information retrieval, data mining and artificial intelligence).

Web structure mining is the discovery of interesting patterns from the hyperlink structure of the web. It involves mining the web document's structure and links aimed at increasing coverage and giving accurate responses to web search queries [7, 24]. The link structure of the web can be used to categorize web documents. It is very useful in determining similarities and differences between sites and web documents.

Web usage mining involves discovering useful information from web surfers' behaviours. In other words, web usage mining is dedicated to mining secondary information extracted from user interactions with the web while surfing. Web usage data consist of data from web server access logs,

browser logs, referrer logs, user profiles, user sessions and profiles, cookies, mouse clicks, and any data resulting from user interaction with the web.

Fig 1 Categories of web mining

III. FRAME WORK OF WEB OULIER MINING

The web is composed of multimedia data of various types from numerous sources. The different sources and data types make automatic discovery of web-based information very challenging. For example, algorithms designed for mining outliers from web servers cannot be applied to web contents, because of the differences in data source and types. To address this problem, web outliers are classified into three groups: web content outliers, web usage outliers, and web structure outliers depending on data source (see Fig. 2).

The taxonomy for web outliers supports the development of content-specific algorithms for mining outliers. Thus, separate algorithms can be designed for mining outliers from web servers, web pages, and the hyperlink structure of the web.

A. The taxonomy for web outliers

1) *Web usage outliers*: exist in web usage data. Web usage data consists of user interactions with the web typically captured by web servers (e.g., server logs, browser log, referrer logs, mouse clicks, etc). Web statistical outlier technique used most often is access frequency analysis. Web documents with high access frequencies are declared very important and their contents are usually moved to the main pages for review. Web usage pattern outliers exist in the usage pattern on the web. For example, a fraction of the 40% of Chapters visitors who purchase book(s) from competitors constitutes web usage pattern usage statistical outliers and web usage pattern outliers

are different types of outliers present in web usage data. Web usage statistical outliers exist in summary statistics of web usage data.

2) *Web content outlier*: is described as page(s) with 'varying contents' which diverges from similar pages taken from the same category. The web contents have data of varying types including textual, video, pictures, etc. Thus, certain pages may be outliers with respect to particular data type or a combination of data types. A formal definition for web content outliers is given below:

Given a set of web documents d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n , and a query vector q_j from category c , if the relative weight between document d_j and query vector q_j is greater than some user defined threshold, then the document d_j constitutes a web content outlier.

3) *Web structure outlier*: The web is a directed graph with nodes corresponding to web pages whose links are edges. A graph is defined as a pair (V, E) , where V is a set of vertices corresponding to web pages and E is a set of edges corresponding to the links. Ideally, linked nodes should contain related information but there are linked nodes that contain information that may not be related. Web structure outliers are links with connecting, nodes containing unrelated information. A web structure outlier is defined below:

A web structure outlier is defined as set of link(s) with unrelated connecting nodes. Given a graph (V, E) where V is a set of pages and E a set of Links. If E_{ij} is the link between V_i and V_j but the contents of V_i and V_j are not related, then the link E_{ij} constitutes a web structure outlier.

Fig. 2 Types of Web Outlier

B. Framework of outlier mining

We suggest outlier mining process is divided into 4 sub tasks shown in fig. 3.

Fig.3 Web Outlier mining frame work

1) *Resource finding*: By Resource finding we mean the process of retrieving information that is online or offline from the text sources available from web such as elct-newsletter, elc-newswire and newsgroups. The text content of HTML documents is obtained by removing HTML tags, and also manual selection of Web resources. We also include text sources such as text database, online text made only for research prepose

2) *Information selection and Pre-processing*: It is any kind of transformation process which retrieves the original data such as IR process. These Transformations processes coude be either kid of pre-processing such as removing stop words, stemming or a pre- processing desired representation such as finding phrase I the training data, transforming representation into relation or first order logic form.

3) *Outlier Detection*: It is the process of automatically describe the pattern at individual Website or in multiple Web sites. Machine learning ad data mining techniques are used for Outlier Detection. We should also notice that human play a important role in knowledge discovery process on Web since Web is an attractive medium .This is also important for validation ad /or interpretation for task four.

4) *Outlier Analysis*: It is the process of validation ad /or interpretation of mined outlier patterns. The final phase of the web outlier mining algorithms involves analysing the outliers returned for decision making. This step usually requires a domain expert to determine why such outliers occur and why they are outliers.

We have argued that every web outlier mining algorithm may go through all the phases but the inputs, outputs, and the processes may be different for different outlier mining algorithms. For example, resource extraction for web content and web structure outlier mining involves downloading documents using web crawlers while in web usage outlier mining, the data to be mined is retrieved from web servers. Preprocessing in web usage outlier mining may involve performing tasks like path completion, path identification, and

user identification whereas in web content outlier mining it may include stop-word removal, stemming, etc.

C. Techniques of Web outlier Mining

We suggest different types of Techniques to mine outliers form Web Data Sets and retrieve useful information and patterns from the World Wide Web documents and services.

- *Clustering*: Clustering of users help to discover groups of users with similar navigation patterns for Example providing personalized Web content. Clustering of pages help to discover groups of pages having related content. The clustering based techniques involve a clustering step which partitions the data into groups which contain similar objects. The assumed behaviour of outliers is that they either do not belong to any cluster, or belong to very small clusters, or are forced to belong to a cluster where they are very different from other members. Similarly, the normal instances belong to dense and large clusters. This distinction makes it possible to separate out the outliers from the rest of the data.
- *Classification*: Classification is the technique to map a data item into one of several predefined classes. It is used to develop profile of users belonging to a particular class or category. Classification is an important machine learning and data mining concept. The primary aim of classification is to learn a set of labelled data instances (*training*) and then classify an unseen instance into one of the learnt class (*testing*). Outlier detection techniques based on classification also operate in the same two-phase fashion, using *normal* and *outlier* as the two classes. The training phase builds a classification model using the available labelled training data. The testing phase classifies a test instance using the model learnt. The techniques following this approach fall under supervised outlier detection techniques. Certain techniques inject artificial outliers into normal training data and obtain fully labelled training data.
- *Association Rules*: Rule based techniques generate rules which either capture the normal behaviour of a system. Any instance that is not covered by any such rule is considered as an outlier. It is used to discover correlations among pages accessed together by a client It helps the restructure of Web site, Page pre-fetching ad to develop e-commerce marketing strategies.
- *Sequential Patterns*: Extract frequently occurring inter-session patterns such that the presence of a set of items followed by another item in time order. It is used to predict future user visit patterns for example placing ads or recommendations at various Web sites.

- *Dependency Modeling*: Determine if there are any significant dependencies among the variables in the Web domain. For Example predict future Web resource consumption, Develop business strategies to increase sales, Improve navigational convenience of users.
- *Kohonen SOM*: Conventional Clustering and association techniques do not necessarily have crisp boundaries therefore, they do not provide crisp classes which are not suitable for real world application .Kohonen SOM(Self Organization Map) is used to find web outlier in temporal based web usage mining using non conventional clustering techniques as Fuzzy and rough sets in web mining applications.
- *Nearest Neighborhood*: Nearest neighbour analysis is a widely used concept in machine learning and data mining in which a data object is analysed with respect to its nearest neighbours. The salient feature of nearest neighbour based outlier detection techniques is that they have an explicit notion of proximity, defined in the form of a distance or similarity measure for any two individual data instances, or a set of instances or a sequence of instances. Given a k and n , a point p is an outlier, if the distance to its k th nearest neighbour is smaller than the corresponding value for no more than $n-1$ other points. This scheme defines the outlier score of a point as the distance from its k th -nearest neighbour. This definition relies on the value of the k (size of the nearest neighbour set).
- *LOF-Algorithm*: compute the density of regions in the data and declare the instances in low dense regions as outliers. An outlier score to any given data point, known as Local Outlier Factor (LOF), depending on its distance from its local neighbourhood. Thus this scheme finds the local outlier score of any data point and is not affected by the variations in the density of distribution of the data.
- *LCS- Mining*: Density-based approach to outlier-mining makes monitoring customer activities even more interesting since every customer activity has a potential of being exceptional (outlier). Littoral Combat Ship (LCS) -Mining contributes an enhancement to the Local Outlier Factor (LOF) algorithm which improves upon the response time of LOF by avoiding the computation of reach ability distances and local reach ability densities.
- *Hypergraph based Outlier Test*: Most existing detection methods are basically designed for numeric data; however, real-life data such as web pages, business transactions and bioinformatics records always contain categorical data. So it causes difficulty to find reasonable exceptions in the real world applications. A novel outlier mining method based on hyper graph model for categorical data. Since hyper graphs precisely capture the distribution characteristics in data

subspaces, this method is effective in identifying anomalies in dense subspaces and presents good interpretations for the local outlier ness. By selecting the most relevant subspaces, the problem of "curse of dimensionality" in very large databases can also be ameliorated.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The success of electronic commerce on the web has contributed to its popularity and hence attracted industrial support for web mining research. Classifying web pages into predefined categories to aid information search and retrieval is a very common task but sifting through previously classified

documents for those with 'varying contents' is an emerging and open research issue. Although outlier mining is considered critical in the traditional data mining community, it has not yet been given serious consideration in the web mining community.

Web outlier mining is an open research issue with several practical applications in information management, electronic business, and electronic commerce. Mining web outliers may lead to an increased understanding and even the possible discovery of competitors in electronic business.

This paper contributes a formal definition for web outliers and establishes a new taxonomy for web outliers that support the development of algorithms for mining web outliers. Thus, separate algorithms can be designed for finding web outliers from different web data sources (i.e., web servers, web pages, etc.). It also provides a general framework for mining web outliers. It also suggests some techniques for mining Web outliers from Web datasets.

Areas of future research include developing scalable and more efficient algorithms for mining web content, web usage, and web structure outliers. Finally, benchmark data must be established to evaluate the performance of web outlier mining algorithms to support comparison with new algorithms as they emerge.

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